

Occupancy Prediction in Multi-Occupant IoT Environments leveraging Federated Learning

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Abstract—Energy efficiency and energy saving have become crucial issues in the face of increasing energy demand, the need for sustainable solutions, and concerns about climate change. Buildings, as significant contributors to energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, require effective measures for energy optimization that can also be reached by predicting the usage of the building spaces. This paper introduces a data-driven approach combining Internet of Things sensors, Machine Learning, Edge computing, and Federated Learning to predict multi-occupancy in buildings. The proposed approach is used on real data from the ICAR-CNR IoT Laboratory in order to extract insights into occupancy patterns within a multi-occupant environment. Finally, a comparative analysis conducted by varying Federated Learning configurations demonstrates the robustness of the solution.

Index Terms—Internet of Things, Federated Learning, Edge Computing, Neural Networks, LSTM, Artificial Intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy efficiency has become a crucial issue due to the increasing demand for energy, the need for sustainable solutions, and growing concerns about climate change. Among various sectors, buildings hold a pivotal position in energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, underscoring the urgency for implementing effective energy-saving measures [1]. Improving energy efficiency in buildings can significantly reduce energy waste by lowering operating costs. However, these enhancements must always consider the occupant's comfort.

One of the key factors in achieving energy efficiency in buildings is optimizing the use of Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems, lighting, and other equipment based on the occupancy information of the individuals in their rooms. In this context, several proposals presented in the literature focus on the detection of room occupancy [2]. These works mainly aim at detecting whether a room is occupied, which is useful for turning on or off equipment like lighting and HVAC systems. Estimating the number

of people in the rooms of a building can be essential for optimizing the HVAC system and achieving maximum energy efficiency [3] [4]. This information can be used to optimize temperature, humidity, and airflow, creating a comfortable environment while minimizing energy consumption. Overestimating or underestimating the number of occupants in a room can result in inefficient use of building systems, leading to wasted energy and increased costs. By accurately estimating occupancy levels, building owners and managers can optimize building systems to meet the needs of occupants, resulting in a more sustainable and comfortable environment [5].

Previous studies have mainly employed traditional techniques, i.e., signal processing or stochastic approaches to estimate and forecast room occupancy. For example, in [2], the authors propose a novel approach that employs WiFi signal strength indicator measurements between transmitter and receiver antennas to estimate and predict the number of individuals in a particular area. The framework exploits the impacts of obstructing the line of sight and scattering effects caused by people. Through the development of a mathematical expression for the probability distribution of received signal amplitude concerning the total number of occupants, the framework leverages Kullback-Leibler divergence for accurate estimation. The proposed framework is validated through extensive indoor and outdoor experiments. [6] introduces a grey-box model for predicting room occupancy and carbon dioxide levels. The model employs stochastic differential equations and can address measurement errors and errors in system description simplification. The model was tested in naturally and mechanically ventilated environments and showed promising occupancy and parameter estimation performance. The research was revealed to be very good at predicting room occupancy, but the methodologies employed are complex and difficult to implement in real-time scenarios. Hence, such drawbacks identified in previous solutions motivated the investigation of the adoption of machine learning (ML), which has recently begun to be explored in the context of forecasting room occupancy. ML techniques can provide higher accuracy with smaller complexity in comparison with former solutions.

The popularity of data-driven approaches based on ML and Deep Learning (DL) [7] for estimating room occupancy is growing due to their ease of implementation and ability to achieve high accuracy. Both ML and DL-based solutions typically collect data using Internet of Things (IoT) [1] [8] sensors/devices and/or cameras and send them to be processed in the cloud so allowing the prediction of room occupancy.

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However, collecting data using cameras can create privacy issues [9]. In order to mitigate these concerns, an alternative approach could be to use sensors for collecting data to estimate occupancy [10]. However, even when using sensors, privacy concerns may still arise during the processing of the collected data on the Cloud. It is important to take appropriate measures to ensure the security and privacy of the data.

To solve this issue, the use of Edge Computing [11] [12] can be considered to process data locally on the devices where data is collected to further reduce the risk of data breaches and unauthorized access. Such devices could also be used to train some models that, according to the Federated Learning (FL) paradigm [13], can be shared in other network nodes without affecting privacy. Among the models available in the literature, a very promising one for predicting events is considered the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network, which is a particular kind of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) [14]. Its ability to capture long-range dependencies and handle sequential data makes it a compelling choice for various applications, including event prediction tasks.

a) Contribution: In this work, we extend the solution proposed in [15], which first introduced an approach for integrating IoT and edge technologies with ML and FL to detect and predict occupancy in a building. While [15] focuses on revealing the presence of individuals in rooms (i.e., a binary classification task) by leveraging a neural architecture based on LSTM, in this work, we consider a more complex scenario.

In more detail, this paper improves the previous research by still integrating IoT and edge technologies with ML and FL, but also exploring the prediction of occupancy for multiple occupants. Moreover, the proposed approach is applied to real-time data collected at the ICAR-CNR headquarters (Rende, Italy) to gain practical insights, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the occupancy patterns and dynamics within a multi-occupant environment. Such data are gathered through a purposely developed IoT-based network. Moreover, in this paper, we conduct a comparative study by analysing several FL configurations, which are obtained by varying different combinations of High-Level Rounds (HLRs) and epochs. HLRs denote the instances when a model is aggregated at a high level, often in the Cloud, while epochs refer training rounds involving clients at the network's edge.

b) Organization of the paper: The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly introduces the theoretical background. Section III discusses previous research in this area, while Section IV thoroughly explains the proposed approach. Section V displays the outcomes of the simulation experiments. Finally, the last section summarizes the conclusions and suggests future research directions.

II. BACKGROUND

In this section, we provide some background information useful to fully understand our proposal. In particular, we focus on fundamental concepts about Machine Learning, Edge Computing, and Federated Learning and how they are connected to the IoT paradigm.

A. Machine Learning

With the advancement of technology, the integration of IoT devices is becoming increasingly prevalent in our daily routines, allowing us to monitor and track our surroundings. This has led to the accumulation of vast amounts of data that can be exploited in several application domains. One very relevant usage of IoT data is for the realization of smart building management systems. In fact, building managers can gather lots of real-time data on factors such as temperature, lighting, and occupancy through IoT sensors. However, manually examining such large volumes of data is not only time-consuming but also prone to errors. As a result, ML is being increasingly utilized to analyze this data and provide accurate information for building management [16]. By employing ML algorithms, the massive amounts of data collected from sensors and other devices can be analyzed and used to gain a deeper understanding of building health and user context [17]. This includes identifying patterns in building usage, predicting occupancy levels, and analyzing energy consumption patterns.

One of the most significant applications of ML in smart building management is the estimation of building occupancy [18]. Machine Learning models can accurately predict the number of occupants in a building or a specific building area by analyzing data collected from various sensors (e.g., passive infrared, CO₂, temperature, humidity, sound, camera). This information can be used to optimize energy consumption and improve occupant comfort by adjusting temperature, lighting, and other building systems. For example, the authors of the paper in [19] implemented a combination of different ML algorithms to estimate the number of occupants in a room through heterogeneous sensor nodes. The proposed approach used low-cost and non-invasive sensors, including CO₂, temperature, lighting, sound, and motion, to accomplish their goal. They utilized supervised learning algorithms, namely Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest (RF), to achieve their target, and their findings were highly satisfactory in terms of accuracy. Similarly, other studies have also explored the use of ML algorithms to predict occupancy in energy-efficient building environments and have reported promising results regarding accuracy and sensitivity [18], [20]. Section III of this paper will briefly explain other works from the literature.

B. Edge Computing

Edge computing uses distributed computing to bring computing power closer to end devices [21] [22] [23]. This technology uses a distributed computing paradigm that can be exploited for various applications like the ones regarding data processing, caching/storage, IoT management, security, and privacy. These applications can execute tasks on edge networks efficiently and effectively to achieve high bandwidth and low latency. This paradigm simplifies the management of end-to-end connections and resources. With an edge-based architecture, data can be produced and consumed closer to the edge itself, reducing the need to transfer data to the center

of the network (e.g., Cloud) to augment security, reliability, and privacy. Combining Artificial Intelligence algorithms with Edge Computing allows it to reduce latency and network load in the network core [24].

For example, the Edge Computing paradigm can be utilized to estimate room occupancy by strategically deploying sensors and cameras to collect data on human movement and activity levels within a given space [25]. The collected data can then be processed and analyzed locally on edge devices, reducing the need for centralized data centers and decreasing the amount of time and resources required to estimate occupancy. For example, the study in [26] introduces a cost-effective edge-based platform for improving energy efficiency in buildings, capable of sensing, processing, and analyzing energy data within residential buildings. The paper describes how the Edge Computing approach has been employed to reduce delay and cost. Similarly, authors in [15] employed Edge Computing as an intermediary layer between the IoT layer and the cloud aggregation layer: the models used were trained on the edge devices themselves, ensuring an enhancement of the data security. Following the local training of models on the edge devices, the cloud aggregator analyzes all the trained models and selects the best one.

The integration of edge computing with artificial intelligence has recently gained momentum in industry and academia. Such integration gave rise to the paradigm known as Edge Intelligence, which leverages the incorporation of machine learning techniques in edge devices. This paradigm is capable of unleashing the real potential of the big data produced by sensor-instrumented environments. One of the techniques that takes advantage of the processing power available at the edge is federated learning.

C. Federated Learning

ML can be effective in estimating room occupancy, but it requires a substantial amount of training data. Data can be collected, for example, from various IoT devices in a building and transmitted to the Cloud to train ML models. Collecting data from different IoT devices and training ML models on a cloud-based server is known as the centralized learning approach. Although a centralized learning approach can provide high accuracy for ML algorithms, it raises privacy concerns when transferring data from IoT devices to the central server. Federated Learning is a viable alternative that permits ML models to be trained on decentralized data without transmitting it to a central server [27] [13] [28]. The model's training is done locally on every device, and the updated models are then sent to a central server for aggregation, so ensuring data privacy and security.

In centralized learning, client data is transmitted to a central server for training, which may raise privacy concerns. In contrast, FL ensures data privacy by storing data locally on clients' devices and training models there. Edge devices are selected to train their models on local data, and their model weights are then sent to the server for aggregation into a global model. Clients use their private datasets to optimize

the global model in each training round, and their updated models are sent back to the server. The server merges the updates following specific rules to create a new global model for the next round of training. Overall, FL enables ML models to be trained on distributed local datasets, preserving privacy and exploiting distributed heterogeneous resources while accurately estimating room occupancy.

III. RELATED WORK

Occupancy prediction in buildings has garnered significant attention due to its potential for optimizing energy efficiency and enhancing occupant comfort. Many studies have focused on leveraging sensor data to estimate occupancy levels in various types of buildings. For instance, [29] proposed an ML-based approach for occupancy prediction for a commercial building. More specifically, this paper investigates the utilization of Multi-Label Classification (MLC) for predicting occupancy, aiming to improve HVAC scheduling efficiency and minimize energy waste. The study conducts a comparative analysis of MLC algorithms and an established approach using data from two commercial buildings. The findings indicate that Support Vector Machine (SVM) and PreHeat exhibit superior performance for rooms with frequent occupancy, while other algorithms show better results for rooms with infrequent occupancy. The paper highlights the importance of considering occupancy frequency and the occupancy state prior to the prediction horizon to enhance prediction accuracy. Similarly, in another paper [30], the authors present multi-sensor fusion methods and a CNN-based solution for occupancy prediction in large indoor environments using low-resolution heat sensors. The experimental results demonstrate the proposed solutions' high accuracy and real-time prediction capabilities. However, [29], [30] are limited to square or rectangular office floor plans, highlighting the need for future work on sensor placement optimization algorithms for complex floor plans and improved sensor fusion methods. Additionally, a study in [31] applies time series modeling to predict occupancy levels in a co-working space in London. By converting sensor-detected occupancy data into time series, the researchers perform exploratory analysis and forecasting. More in particular, the authors employed a SARIMA model for accurate occupancy prediction. The study's findings support decision-making related to daily attendance, required seating capacities, and optimization of the space's design based on predicted occupancy. Heatmap analysis reveals spatial distribution patterns, highlighting the popularity of seats near windows and individual semi-enclosed spaces.

While traditional approaches to occupancy prediction often rely on centralized data aggregation and analysis, recent research has explored the use of FL to address privacy concerns and enable distributed prediction models. For instance, the work by Mahjoub et al. [32] introduces a novel technique for predicting occupancy in smart homes utilizing environmental variables such as CO₂ levels, noise, and relative temperature. The proposed method and forecasting strategy optimize the energy management system by effectively utilizing the electric

heating system. By employing the LSTM neural network and optimizing weight updates using Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), the accuracy of autocorrelation prediction is significantly improved. Another study in [10] focuses on predicting building occupancy by utilizing diverse sensor data and implementing a feature selection algorithm. The sensor data consists of indoor and outdoor conditions, Wi-Fi device connectivity, energy consumption, HVAC operations, and time information. Different deep learning architectures, such as LSTM, Bi-LSTM, GRU, and Bi-GRU, are employed to forecast occupancy in various environments, including offices, libraries, and lecture rooms. The proposed feature selection algorithm demonstrates superior performance compared to existing methods, resulting in improved model accuracy.

Despite the good results presented by the aforementioned related work, they lack a systematic approach devoted to integrating IoT and edge technologies with ML and FL for occupancy prediction in multi-occupant environments. Moreover, none of the work above is devoted to comparing different parameter settings for the used FL approach.

IV. AN APPROACH FOR MULTI-OCCUPANCY PREDICTION

This paper aims to build upon the approach introduced in [15] by extending its capabilities with a more sophisticated FL solution. Specifically, the added enhancement allows the possibility to explore different configurations in the pair High-Level-Rounds/epochs (*HLRs/epochs*). Moreover, the approach is designed for considering multi-occupancy forecasting, combining FL with LSTM networks, and is based on a three-layer architecture, as illustrated in Figure 1, where:

- the *IoT Layer* comprises intelligent IoT devices such as sensors, actuators, and smart objects distributed across specific rooms in a building. These devices play a crucial role in collecting valuable data necessary for training and executing the LSTM model;
- the *Edge Layer* is the intermediate layer and hosts Edge Computing Nodes (ECNs), e.g., users' notebooks, mobiles, or cheap single-board computers. These nodes are strategically deployed close to the sensors at the edge to collect data and calculate their respective models efficiently. This positioning at the edge brings several significant advantages, including limiting communications towards higher edge layers or the Cloud, reducing energy consumption during communication, enhancing data privacy by keeping it close to data producers and ensuring resilience to potential disconnections from the Internet or higher-level networks. Additionally, the ECNs autonomously run their local calculated models, which are updated during the FL process based on newly gathered data. It is important to note that some ECNs may not be capable of training their own models due to various constraints, such as limited computing resources or the absence of sensors to measure real occupancy. In such cases, these ECNs can receive and utilize pre-trained models from the Cloud/Edge Aggregator Layer;

- the *Cloud/Edge Aggregator Layer*: is the upper layer of our architecture and can be deployed both in the Cloud and at the edge, in a node capable of interacting with all the other edge nodes and with sufficient processing capabilities. This layer hosts a Cloud/Edge Aggregator (CEA) which receives models from the Edge Layer, aggregates them, and distributes the merged model to the underlying nodes.

Fig. 1: The reference architecture considered in the proposed approach.

The literature offers several algorithms for merging the models in FL. FedAvg [33] is the first and mostly used algorithm, which merges locally trained models at each HLR. Among the others, FedProx [34] enhances FedAvg with a proximal term and FedNova [35] ensures objective consistency and rapid error convergence through normalized averaging. This paper adopts a weighted strategy based on the most popular FedAvg algorithm.

To better describe the approach and its capabilities to accommodate various configurations (*HLRs/epochs*) for FL, we introduce Algorithm 1. In particular, such an algorithm initiates by sending an initial model from the CEA to all the ECNs. Among the ECNs, those capable of participating in the training phase, since they have sufficient data from the IoT Layer and availability of computation resources, actively collect data from IoT devices and update their internal models. This process is repeated for *Epochs* times, allowing ECNs to refine their models. Then, ECNs send their computed models to the CEA, which merges them and shares the result with the ECNs whenever the newly merged model's F1 score (macro) is greater than the last one's F1 score (macro). All the steps, apart from the initial model sharing phase, are repeated for *HLRs* times so as to make several iterations in the local model training and high-level merge.

This collaborative training approach ensures that all the ECNs, including nodes that can't calculate their own model, can benefit from LSTM (or other) models that have already been trained in other nodes.

Algorithm 1 The FL Approach used with variable *HLRs* and *Epoch* parameters.

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1: procedure LEARN_FL_MODEL(HLRs, Epochs)
2:   currH = 0, currE = 0
3:   sendModel(CEA, ECNs)
4:   ▷ the initial model is sent to the ECN nodes at the edge
5:   while currH < HLRs do
6:     while currE < Epochs do
7:       gatherIoTData(ECNs)
8:       ▷ the ECNs gather data from the IoT devices
9:       updateEdgeModel(ECNs)
10:      ▷ the ECNs update their internal model
11:      currE ++
12:      sendModel(ECNs, CEA)
13:      ▷ ECNs send their updated models to the CEA
14:      mergeModel(CEA)
15:      ▷ CEA merges the updated models from the ECNs
16:      if mergedModel(CEA).F1Score > lastmodel
17:      then
18:        sendModel(CEA, ECNs)
19:        ▷ CEA sends the merged model to the ECNs only if the
20:        ▷ F1 Score of the new Model is greater than the last one
21:      currH ++

```

V. EXPERIMENTS

The approach presented in Section IV has been tested in a real case study, which will be discussed in the following subsections. In more detail, Section V-A provides an overview of our case study and details the deployment used and the setup of the system, while Section V-B showcases the obtained simulation results.

A. Case Study Setup

The case study focused on creating an occupancy prediction system for the ICAR-CNR Institute building located in Rende, Italy. In such a building, we deployed several sensors in all the rooms so to understand occupancy and forecast it for all the users. Anyway, in this case study, we will focus only on the real data collected in the Internet of Things Laboratory, where we developed a system comprehending sensors and actuators of different technologies and several Raspberry Pi 4s, acting as ECNs and responsible for collecting and processing data. In particular, for our case study, we used a ZigBee light sensor (Xiaomi Mijia Smart Light Sensor), a ZigBee passive infrared (PIR) sensor (Philips Hue Motion Sensor), and a WiFi CO₂ sensor (in the Gases Sensor Board Pro of the Waspote WiFi Pro¹). In order to complement the devices required for the experiments, we also implemented a Virtual Sensor, using a touchscreen connected to one of the ECNs, to obtain accurate data on occupancy. During the data collection periods, occupants in the laboratory used this touchscreen to indicate their presence. This touchscreen was also used to visualize the most recent data in the laboratory through a Node-Red application. All the devices used for this case study are shown in Figure 2.

¹Waspote Gases Sensor Board Pro. https://development.libelium.com/gases_pro_sensor_guide/gases-pro-sensor-board-calibrated

Fig. 2: The devices involved in the implemented case study.

Starting from this system, two datasets were created with data from light, CO₂, PIR, and virtual touchscreen sensors: the first one comprehends 17 days gathered in the month of November 2022, and the second one contains 5 days taken in October 2022. Both datasets present data collected during working hours with a timestep of one minute between two tuples, and the data collected is limited to represent zero, one, or two people. It is worth noting that the approach proposed is general and would also be applied to data showing more occupants in the considered environment. In order to use the approach reported in Section IV, we emulated to have, in the first dataset, data from ten different rooms with similar patterns of use. So, this dataset has been divided into eleven segments. Among these, ten segments are used for training models at distinct emulated ECNs. The remaining segment is utilized as a validation set encompassing all ECNs. It is worth noting that, prior to using the data for forecasting, some data preprocessing (e.g., handling missing values, data normalization, and data transformation to 3D structure) is done to prepare the raw data stored in the datasets, making it suitable for the LSTM network training.

We have implemented the approach using *Google Colaboratory*², *Python*³ (Release 3.7.0) and libraries like *TensorFlow*⁴ (version 2.8.2), *TensorFlow Federated*⁵ (version 0.16.1), and *Pandas*⁶ (version 1.3.5). The proposed model incorporates specialized LSTM with one layer having 32 units and another having 16 units. These LSTM layers effectively capture temporal dependencies, enabling the model to learn long-term patterns. To prevent overfitting, two dropout layers with a 0.10 dropout rate are utilized, encouraging robust learning. The final dense layer generates continuous numerical predictions. The activation function used for LSTM is the hyperbolic tangent (tanh), facilitating efficient information flow and preventing issues like exploding gradients. The model has been trained to predict the occupancy 10 timesteps

²Google Colaboratory, <https://research.google.com/colaboratory/>

³Python 3.7.0. <https://www.python.org/downloads/release/python-370/>

⁴TensorFlow. <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

⁵TensorFlow Federated. <https://www.tensorflow.org/federated>

⁶Pandas. <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

ahead (occupancy at the tenth minute in the future) using the previous 60 observations (sixty minutes in the past) as input in each case. The (*HLRs/epochs*) couples compared in the following, and hereafter represented as "FL-Model (*HLRs, epochs*)," are: FL-Model(50, 2), FL-Model(20, 5), FL-Model(10, 10), FL-Model(5, 20), and FL-Model(2, 50). Moreover, all the cases above will be compared with a centralized case, in which there is no training at the ECNs in the edge, but all the data for training the only centralized model will always be sent to a centralized node. It is worth noting that the initial centralized model consists of the LSTM introduced above.

B. Numerical results

This section is devoted to illustrating the quantitative results achieved in terms of the evaluation measures used to demonstrate the quality of the proposed approach. Specifically, the predictive performances of the models were assessed using the following well-known metrics: *Accuracy*, *Precision*, *Recall*, *AUC* (Area Under the ROC Curve), *F1 Score* (a harmonic mean of Precision and Recall), and the *Mean Absolute Error* (MAE). Except for Accuracy and MAE, all metrics were computed using a Macro-Averaging scheme, furnishing a per-class average for each measure.

Table I reports the results obtained by varying configurations of the FL-Model, particularly by considering different values of *HLR* and epochs. Additionally, we present the performance of the model trained in a centralized way against the complete dataset. This serves as a benchmark, representing an ideal yet unrealistically centralized scenario where all data are available in a single node for analysis. While FL-Model(20, 5) strikes an optimal balance between precision and recall, FL-Model(10, 10) delivers competitive results while demanding reduced communication with the coordinator node. Notably, at each HLR iteration of the FL process, the performances of the current model are compared with the ones of the model trained in the previous iteration. If the new model exhibits a higher F1-Score on the validation set, then the current model is updated. The learning algorithm proceeds without any model updates if the new model doesn't improve. This behavior influences the results on the test set; specifically, when the model is not updated, its accuracy remains constant over the epochs.

Moreover, we illustrate how the values of these metrics change as the number of epochs increases, as depicted in Figures 3, where we print a point per merge in the CEA (per each HLR). As expected, the number of epochs plays a key role; indeed, with the increasing number of iterations, we also observe an improvement in the predictive performances of each model.

Finally, in Figure 4, we show in detail the real occupancy as in the testset and compare it with the predicted ones according to all the cases introduced above.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in developing efficient and energy-saving solutions to tackle the challenges posed by rising energy demand and climate change. Buildings' energy consumption and emissions underscore the importance of energy-saving strategies. In particular, comfort and safety in the building can be improved by leveraging Artificial Intelligence techniques to monitor environmental variables (e.g., the occupancy), but it requires coping with a number of issues, such as limited computational resources, privacy, and data noise. To address these issues, in this work, we devised a solution integrating Internet of Things and edge technologies with Machine Learning and Federated Learning to predict building occupancy. Unlike previous works that focused on single-occupancy prediction, this paper focuses on multi-occupant scenarios. An experimental analysis conducted on real data demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

In future work, we plan to delve into more sophisticated neural architectures capable of adeptly capturing and representing long-range dependencies in sequential data. A specific avenue of interest is the integration of Temporal Convolutional Neural Networks, renowned for their proficiency in this domain. Moreover, we plan to extend the implemented model to recognize and predict not only the occupancy but also some specific activities. Finally, we want to enhance our case study by comprehending all the rooms in the building of our research institute.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partially supported by (i) European Union - NextGenerationEU - National Recovery and Resilience Plan (Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza, PNRR) - Project: "SoBigData.it - Strengthening the Italian RI for Social Mining and Big Data Analytics" - Prot. IR0000013 - Avviso n. 3264 del 28/12/2021; (ii) the Italian MUR, PRIN 2022 Project "COCOWEARS" (A framework for COntinuum COmputing WEARable Systems), CUP: B53D23013190006; (iii) the National Research Council of Italy (CNR), "Le Scienze per le TRansizioni Industriale, Verde ed Energetica" - Towards Sustainable Cognitive Buildings (ToSCoB) project; and (iv) Brazilian Funding Agencies FAPERJ and CNPq for Prof. Flavia Delicato.

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TABLE I: Evaluation metrics computed for different configurations and comparison with the fully centralized solution. All the metrics are calculated by using a Macro-Averaging scheme. Bold values highlight the best configuration for a given measure.

Configuration	MAE	Accuracy	Macro Precision	Macro Recall	Macro F1	Macro AUC
FL-Model (50, 2)	0.160	0.850	0.860	0.820	0.840	0.850
FL-Model (20, 5)	0.174	0.836	0.860	0.791	0.816	0.854
FL-Model (10, 10)	0.176	0.831	0.865	0.786	0.814	0.854
FL-Model (5, 20)	0.201	0.813	0.809	0.763	0.781	0.818
FL-Model (2, 50)	0.192	0.819	0.831	0.766	0.789	0.829
Centralized Model	0.173	0.850	0.845	0.820	0.842	0.854

Fig. 3: Evaluation metrics curves computed against the test set on increasing number of epochs.

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Fig. 4: Actual vs Predicted occupancy for the considered case study.

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